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American and Polish Migration Laws in Light of the Border Crises. Remarks Inspired by *Biden v. Texas*

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Abstract:

In light of the crises at the Polish–Belarusian and American–Mexican borders, Poland and the United States introduced many controversial from the human rights point of view changes in their migration laws. The aim of this article is to show and compare these reforms, as well as the jurisprudence which concerned them. Of particular importance is the opinion of the Supreme Court of U.S. in *Biden v. Texas*, as the inspiration and starting point for this article.

Keywords: *Biden v. Texas*, migration law, push-back, Migrant Protection Protocols, Polish–Belarusian border, U.S.–Mexican border

Amerykańskie i polskie prawa migracyjne w świetle kryzysów na granicach. Uwagi inspirowane orzeczeniem *Biden v. Texas*

W obliczu kryzysu na granicach polsko-białoruskiej i amerykańsko-meksykańskiej Polska oraz Stany Zjednoczone wprowadziły liczne i kontrowersyjne z prawnoczułowieczego punktu widzenia zmiany w swoich prawach migracyjnych. Celem niniejszego artykułu jest przedstawienie, a następnie porównanie tychże reform oraz orzecznictwa, które ich dotyczyło. Szczególny nacisk położony zostanie na orzeczenie Sądu Najwyższego USA

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w sprawie *Biden v. Texas*, jako na orzeczenie będące inspiracją i punktem wyjścia dla tego artykułu.

Słowa kluczowe: *Biden v. Texas*, granica amerykańsko-meksykańska, granica polsko-białoruska, prawo migracyjne, push-back, Migrant Protection Protocols

1. Introduction

The main aim of this article is to show and compare how jurisprudences of the United States of America (here: Supreme Court of the US² in the case *Biden v. Texas*³) and Republic of Poland (here: Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok in numerous cases) have dealt with the migration crises on, respectively, U.S.–Mexican and Polish–Belarusian borders starting in 2019 and 2020. This article focuses on the situation of migrants illegally crossing the borders and migrants who, in the American context, are deemed „inadmissible”, which according to the definition in the Immigration and Nationality Act (INA)⁴ means migrants, who „by fraud or willfully misrepresenting a material fact, seeks to procure (or has sought to procure or has procured) a visa, other documentation, or entry into the United States or other benefit provided under this chapter”⁵ or who is not in possession of the required travel documents (such as e.g. visa) at the time of crossing the border⁶ (later referred to in the text as: migrants).

The issue at hand is important and quite sensitive. „Illegal” migration, in this text understood strictly as illegal border crossing, has been a huge topic in media of different sorts and literature in both countries, especially around the time for elections. The alleged dangers posed by migrants will not be the subject of this article. The text below focuses on the human rights aspects of this problem, mostly on the initiative the U.S. and Poland have undertaken in order to somehow deal with the crises at their borders.

The initial hypothesis is that, if the U.S. and Poland are countries of different political structure, geopolitical position and legal systems, then the measures adopted by them would be adequately different from each other. After some preliminary research (even a quick look at the INA and the Polish Act on Foreigners) it would seem that there are some similarities to the way of addressing crises on these countries’ borders than the general knowledge about those states would suggest. The following article is supposed to explore and prove or debunk the preliminary hypothesis, and it is supposed to do so based on dogmatic method (analysis of the most important statutes

² Later in the text also referred to as: SCOTUS.

³ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785, 142 S.Ct. 2528, 213 L.Ed.2d 956 (2022).

⁴ Immigration and Nationality Act, 8 U.S.C. § 1101 et seq.

⁵ Immigration and Nationality Act, 8 U.S.C. §1182(a)(6)(C).

⁶ Immigration and Nationality Act, 8 U.S.C. §1183(a)(7).

for both countries in question) and in-depth analysis of *Biden v. Texas* judgment (the core of this article), as well as some analysis of chosen Polish cases. All the Polish cases that are cited in the article are one of the recent ones and they „cement” all the case-law created previously. These judgments represent the basic findings and rulings of the courts, showing the strongest arguments for the legality or illegality of the measures adopted by the Polish legislator. Moreover, the article focuses mostly on the ramifications of *Biden v. Texas* and American migration policies and law, which is why the part about Polish migration law is significantly shorter than the part about MPP and the SCOTUS ruling. The construction of the article is a result of a conscious decision of the author.

The plan of this article is as follows. First, the migration policies of the U.S. and Poland will be shortly introduced and described: how they came into being, how they functioned, what was their outcome and with what kind of response from the general public they met. This part is supposed to make it easier for the reader to see the resemblances in both of them, as well as to better understand the holding in *Biden v. Texas* and the Polish jurisprudence, which will be further analyzed in the next segment of the article. The opinion of the Supreme Court in *Biden v. Texas* serves as an inspiration to this article, and – as a central point of it – will be closely examined. Then, the way the Polish administrative courts viewed a very similar problem will be shown, in a kind of juxtaposition to the Supreme Court’s opinion.

2. Migration policies in the U.S. and Poland

Although, as will be shown in the next part of the article, the Supreme Court of the United States in *Biden v. Texas* did not concern itself with the matter of legality of MPP, in order to have a better, wider view at this issue, it is worthwhile to take a look at both the American and Polish regulations from the perspective of its compliance with pre-existing system of law. In order to do so, one has to understand the international law implications first.

Main rules that apply to the situations at the U.S.–Mexican and Polish–Belarusian borders, can be found in the United Nations Conventions. Firstly, article 33 of the Convention of July 28, 1951 relating to the Status of Refugees (Refugee Convention) prohibits the *non-refoulement* practice, which means expelling or returning a refugee to the territory where his life or freedom would be threatened. Secondly, article 3 of the Convention of December 10, 1984 against Torture (CAT) bans expelling, returning and extraditing a person to another state, where there are substantial grounds to believe he would be in danger or subjected to torture. While in Poland the direct use of these articles is guaranteed by articles 9 and 91 of the Constitution of Republic of Poland, in the U.S. they are implemented into 8 U.S.C.⁷ § 1231. Furthermore, the United States’ obligations have been acknowledged in the juris-

⁷ United States Code (in the text as: U.S.C.).

prudence of the Supreme Court, e.g. in *INS v. Cardoza-Fonseca*⁸, where the Court held the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) is obligated to provide protection to all who meet the statutory qualifications under the INA and CAT. In the Polish context, on the other hand, the importance and binding effect of the European Convention of Human Rights and jurisprudence the European Court of Human Rights cannot be forgotten. The issues that come up frequently in cases involving Poland are connected with the understanding and application of art. 3 (prohibition of torture) and 13 (right to an effective remedy) of the ECHR, as well as art. 4 (territorial application) of Protocol no 4 to the ECHR, and the fact remains that there is a serious systematic violation of the aforementioned rules in that the migrants are denied access to asylum (through the practice of pushbacks or collective expulsions of aliens) and effective remedies – such were the judgments in e.g. *M.K. and others v. Poland*⁹ or *D.A. and others v. Poland*¹⁰. Sadly, those verdicts have not yet resulted in any significant changes in the practice of Polish authorities.

2.1. The Migrant Protection Protocols

At the end of 2018 the United States observed a significant spike in numbers of aliens who in the light of the INA are „inadmissible”, trying to cross the American–Mexican border, with about 2.000 of them each day¹¹. Migrant Protection Protocols (MPP) were introduced in January 2019 in order to combat this situation. They allowed for certain aliens to be returned to Mexico, where they were to stay for the duration of their immigration proceedings¹². Initially, this action was coordinated by both the U.S. and Mexico, in that the latter was supposed to provide migrants with humanitarian protections for as long as they stayed on Mexican territory. As a result of this initiative at least 70.000 people were returned to Mexico between January 1, 2019 and December 31, 2020¹³, which is – unlike Justice Kavanaugh in his concurring opinion in *Biden*

⁸ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 9.3.1987, *INS v. Cardoza-Fonseca*, 480 U.S. 421, 107 S.Ct. 1207, 94 L.Ed.2d 434 (1987).

⁹ Judgment of the European Court of Human Rights of 23.7.2020, *M.K. and others v. Poland*, application nos 40503/17, 42902/17 and 43643/17.

¹⁰ Judgment of the European Court of Human Rights of 22.11.2021, *D.A. and others v. Poland*, application no 51246/17.

¹¹ *Southwest Border Migration FY 2019*, <<https://www.cbp.gov/newsroom/stats/sw-border-migration/fy-2019>>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

¹² D. Kanstroom, *Immigration Law: Current Challenges, Volatility, and Hope*, „Massachusetts Continuing Legal Education, Inc”, IPM MA-CLE 1–1, 2022; D.E. Anker, § A1:5. *Policies limiting access to asylum at the U.S.-Mexico border* [in:] *Law of Asylum in the United States*, LOAUS APP A § A1:5, 2023.

¹³ *The „Migrant Protection Protocols”*, <<https://www.americanimmigrationcouncil.org/research/migrant-protection-protocols>>, [accessed: 19.3.2024]. Different studies show that from 2019 to 2021 between 71.000 and 78.000 people were returned to Mexico. I. Gil-Everaert, C. Masferrer, S.R. Chávez, *Concurrent Displacements: Return, Waiting for Asylum, and Internal Displacement in Northern Mexico*, „Journal on Migration and Human Security” 2023, Vol. 11 (1), p. 131.

v. Texas claimed¹⁴ – a pretty serious and impressive (not at all from the good reasons) number.

What is important in the context of MPP is the 8 U.S.C. § 1225(b)(2)(A), which says that in general, „inadmissible” aliens shall be detained in special detention centers for immigrants¹⁵. However, due to the overpopulation in these centers and there being a real crisis at the border, MPP made use of the section 1225(b)(2)(C), which said that when the detention is not possible, the alien may be returned to the territory they came from. What has also changed with MPP, was the attitude towards asylum seeking migrants. Prior to MPP it was the officers who had to actively ask migrants, whether they fear persecution in their home country. Now, the burden of proof and initiative lays entirely on the migrants¹⁶, which can cause problems, because of problems with accessing legal services. The Trump administration, which introduced MPP, claimed that it „will provide a safer and more orderly process, that will discourage individuals from attempting illegal entry and making false claims to stay in the U.S., and allow more resources to be dedicated to individuals who legitimately qualify for asylum”¹⁷.

What is also important in this context, is that MPP were not the only initiative which allowed for returning some groups of migrants to the territory they came from, in order to battle the migration crisis at the American–Mexican border. Return to Mexico was or could be a consequence of Transit Country Asylum Ban (enacted in July, 2019), Prompt Asylum Case Review (enacted in October, 2019), Humanitarian Asylum Review Program (enacted in October 2019) and Asylum Cooperation Agreement (enacted in November, 2019)¹⁸. These programs are not the subject of this article. They have been mentioned to show the complexity and sometimes even inconsistency of the American migration law. The conclusion is that terminating only MPP is would not immediately change the situation of migrants for the better, as the U.S. migration politics are much more complicated. All the above mentioned initiatives are closely intertwined with each other, which indeed poses a challenge for legislator.

Returned migrants faced a lot of challenges, both with the administrative proceedings still pending in the U.S., and with the conditions they were to live. Studies show

¹⁴ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 815.

¹⁵ More on how these detention centers function in the U.S. on <<https://www.ice.gov/detention-facilities>>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

¹⁶ A. Mukpo, *Asylum-Seekers Stranded in Mexico Face Homelessness, Kidnapping, and Sexual Violence*, <<https://www.aclu.org/issues/immigrants-rights/immigrants-rights-and-detention/asylum-seekers-stranded-mexico-face>>, [accessed: 19.3.2024].

¹⁷ *Migrant Protection Protocols*, <<https://www.dhs.gov/news/2019/01/24/migrant-protection-protocols>>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

¹⁸ J. Bolter, M. Chishti, *Interlocking Set of Trump Administration Policies at the U.S.-Mexico Border Bars Virtually All from Asylum*, Table 1, <<https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/interlocking-set-policies-us-mexico-border-bars-virtually-all-asylum>>, [accessed: 17.3.2024].

that their prospects of finding and having a legal attorney were seven times worse than if they had been in the United States, not to mention that the wait for the first hearing was significantly longer for those under MPP¹⁹. The proceedings themselves, instead of getting shorter, have lengthened to almost two years of waiting for a decision²⁰. As for what awaited migrants in Mexico²¹, one of the greatest challenges was to find a place to stay, due to overcrowding. People affected by MPP were unable to find legal employment and were not allowed to move from the place they stayed in (that included a ban on international movement). That caused another set of obstacles. Many reported also being victims of violence (physical, sexual, death threats, kidnapping etc.)²². Having considered all that, it can be said that allegations of MPP violating international law, are not so out of place, and in fact have some credit.

As it happened, these matters were acknowledged in American courts. In 2020 in *Innovations Law Lab v. Wolf*²³, the Court of Appeals in the Ninth District held that the petitioners (non-Mexican asylum seekers) were likely to succeed on merits of claim that MPP were inconsistent with Immigration and Nationality Act (INA), because INA's contiguous territory return provision did not apply to *bona fide* asylum seekers, as well as on merits of claim that MPP did not comply with treaty-based *non-refoulement* obligations codified in INA. However, the case was later vacated as moot by *Innovations Law Lab v. Mayorkas*²⁴, in which the question of MPP's legality was posed. In this case the Court of Appeals in the Ninth Circuit vacated its judgment and remanded the case to the District Court. Even though the law created in these cases is not currently at force, it shows that the courts have faced the issue of MPP's legality, giving some arguments as to why there are problems with MPP's compliance with national and international law.

When it comes to the situation at the U.S.–Mexican border, according to the survey²⁵ conducted at the beginning of 2024 most adults (78% respondents) viewed it as a problem of some kind (with 45% saying it is a crisis). A large group (80%) criticized the actions

¹⁹ *Contrasting Experiences: MPP vs. Non-MPP Immigration Court Cases*, <<https://trac.syr.edu/immigration/reports/587/>>, [accessed: 19.3.2024].

²⁰ I. Gil-Everaert, C. Masferrer, S.R. Chávez, *Concurrent...*, p. 131–132.

²¹ I. Gil-Everaert, C. Masferrer, S.R. Chávez, *Concurrent...*, p. 131–132.

²² K. Hampton, M. Heisler, R. Mishori, J. Naples-Mitchell, E. Raker *et al.*, *Forced into Danger: Human Rights Violations Resulting from the U.S. Migrant Protection Protocols*, <<https://phr.org/our-work/resources/forced-into-danger/>>, [accessed: 19.3.2024].

²³ Decision of the United States Court of Appeals, Ninth Circuit of 28.2020, *Innovations Law Lab v. Wolf*, 951 F.3d 1073 (2020), p. 1083–1085.

²⁴ Decision of the United States Court of Appeals, Ninth Circuit of 6.8.2021, *Innovations Law Lab v. Mayorkas*, 5 F.4th 1099 (2021).

²⁵ *How Americans View the Situation at the U.S.–Mexico Border, Its Causes and Consequences*, <<https://www.pewresearch.org/politics/2024/02/15/how-americans-view-the-situation-at-the-u-s-mexico-border-its-causes-and-consequences/>>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

taken by the government. Another survey's findings show²⁶ that the percent of U.S. adults deeming this situation a „crisis” has not changed in 2023, when compared with 2019 (changes are visible only when one looks at the results categorized by partisanship: the number of Americans thinking of the situation at the border grew among Republicans and Independents, but fell dramatically among Democrats, which could be somehow argued by the change in administration in 2021). Worth noticing is, that the majority (irregardless of partisanship) are sympathetic towards migrants and immigrants, even when it comes to the migrants (the exception being among Republican respondents, among whom „only” 48% feel sympathetic towards immigrants crossing the US border illegally)²⁷.

2.2. Crisis on the Polish–Belarusian border and following changes in the migration law

According to the statistics of the Polish Border Guard, there was a significant surge in numbers of migrants trying to illegally cross the Polish–Belarusian border in 2021. Almost 40.000 people crossed this particular border illegally, according to some data²⁸, however the total number of people crossing and/or attempting to cross the border could be much higher due to the practice of pushbacks. The data shared with the public was not clear in that regard. It has to be pinpointed, that never before in Polish contemporary history (since the end of the second world war) had Poland faced such a challenge when it comes to migration policies²⁹. This whole crisis had its beginning in actions of the Belarusian regime, which first, under false pretences, encouraged migrants to come to Belarus, where they would get a tourist visa and easier access to the EU territories. The fact remains that migrants wanted to cross the EU border in the first place, but that was the only objective they shared with the Belarusian regime. The latter's main aim was to destabilize the situation in Poland and so the migrants were driven to the Polish–Belarusian border and more often than not forced or assisted to try to cross it, more often than not experiencing violence and threats from Belarusian officers³⁰. The situation was widely described and talked about in media and literature, as an element of hybrid war³¹. This aspect will not be, however,

²⁶ *Plurality in U.S. Says Southern Border Situation Is 'Crisis'*, <<https://news.gallup.com/poll/508565/plurality-say-southern-border-situation-crisis.aspx>>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

²⁷ *Plurality...* This result is still kind of impressive.

²⁸ *Nielegalne przekroczenia granicy z Białorusią w 2021 r.*, <<https://www.strazgraniczna.pl/pl/aktualnosci/9689,Nielegalne-przekroczenia-granicy-z-Bialorusia-w-2021-r.html>>, [accessed: 17.3.2024].

²⁹ B. Mikołajczyk, *Pacta sunt servanda pod presją migracyjną. Uwagi na temat kryzysu na polsko-białoruskiej granicy*, in: *Rządy prawa jako wartość uniwersalna. Księga jubileuszowa Profesora Krzysztofa Wójtowicza*, ed. A. Kozłowski, Wrocław 2022, p. 473.

³⁰ B. Mikołajczyk, *Pacta...*, p. 471.

³¹ More on hybrid war aspects on the Polish–Belarusian border in: K. Chochowski, *Kryzys na granicy polsko-białoruskiej jako przejaw wojny hybrydowej. Aspekty administracyjnoprawne*, „Roczniki Nauk

the object of further analysis here. It should be noted, however, that due to the Belarusian regime's actions there could be no such cooperation between both countries with regard to how they shape their migration policies as it was between the U.S. and Mexico (as mentioned above). Therefore, the impact of pushbacks at the Polish–Belarusian border could warily be described as worse, in that the pushed-back migrants could not have applied for asylum from the Belarusian territory, as was the case with Mexico.

At the time, there was already a regulation in force, which revolved around the circumstances of possible border crossing³². The legal basis for the regulation of March 13, 2020 was article 16 section 3 point 2, which allowed the Minister of Internal Affairs and Administration to issue a regulation temporarily suspending or restricting the traffic at the border, when it was deemed necessary due to the matters of national security, public safety, public health or human life. In 2020 it was the COVID-19 pandemic, which was the cornerstone for this regulation, however the August 20, 2021 amendment was more about responding to other events in the neighboring country (such as false elections in Belarus followed by repressions of the opposition) and solving the problem of growing numbers of migrants at the Polish–Belarusian border³³. Before August 2021 the aforementioned regulation concerned people who had neither Polish Ukrainian or Belarusian citizenship, nor a right to legally work, study or stay in Poland³⁴ – their entry onto the territory of Poland was restricted, but not entirely prohibited. The amendment, however, added to paragraph 3 of this regulation sections 2a and 2b, which essentially allowed border guard officers to return aliens, who did not meet the criteria set in section 2, to be returned to the „border line”, without having started a proper administrative procedure first. It mostly affected all these migrants, who tried to cross the border outside border posts. Important is, that a huge number of these aliens had no possibility to file a motion for international protection before being returned to the Belarusian territory.

Later on, on October 14, 2021 some important statutes in Polish migration law were amended, including the Act of December 12, 2003 on Foreigners and Act of June 13, 2003 on granting protection to foreigners on the territory of the Republic of Poland.

Spółecznych” 2021, Vol. 13 (49), No. 4, p. 81–99; M. Lorek, G. Wierzbicki, M. Więckiewicz, G. Surowiecki, *Migracja na granicy polsko-białoruskiej jako przejaw wojny hybrydowej*, „Polityka i Społeczeństwo” 2023, Vol. 3 (21), p. 179–187; M. Zdanowicz, *The Migration Crisis on the Polish-Belarusian Border*, „Białostockie Studia Prawnicze” 2023, Vol. 28, No. 1, p. 103–115.

³² Regulation of the Minister of the Interior Affairs and Administration of 13.3.2020 on the temporary suspension or declaration of foreign traffic on the most fortunate border points (Journal of Laws of Republic of Poland of 2023, item 1403).

³³ Regulation of the Minister of the Interior Affairs and Administration of 20.8.2021 amending the regulation on the temporary suspension or declaration of foreign traffic on the most fortunate border points (Journal of Laws of Republic of Poland, item 1536).

³⁴ § 3 section 2 of the Regulation of 13.3.2020 on the temporary suspension or declaration of foreign traffic on the most fortunate border points (Journal of Laws of Republic of Poland of 2023, item 1403).

These changes led to there being another legal ground for issuing and immediately executing a decision to leave the territory of Republic of Poland³⁵ on a completely new basis. Previously, a foreigner could have been issued such a decision if their visa or their visa-free stay in Poland expired³⁶. This particular amendment made it possible to oblige a foreigner to leave Poland immediately after they had crossed the border illegally. Even after filing an appeal, the execution of this decision is not stopped, which makes appealing *de facto* impossible, due to lack of legal help provided to migrants (in sufficient amount and quality), as well as problems with delivering them the final decision to the Belarusian territory. Notable is, that in comparison to MPP, Polish regulations do not say what happens, if the detention centers are overcrowded, and therefore there is no possibility to admit new migrants. There is no such rule in Polish law as section 1225(b)(2)(C), even though Poland also faces, or is likely to face in the future, the problem of overpopulation in such centers.

However, that does not mean that Polish regulations, which initially aimed at battling the crisis on the Polish–Belarusian border, are any more compliant with the international law about *non-refoulement* (*supra*) than American. Next to the issues with international law prohibiting *non-refoulement* to countries, where there is potential risk to one's life or freedoms (as is the case with Belarusian regime here), debatable is, whether the regulation of March 13, 2020, due to its statutory authorization (legal basis for releasing a minister's regulation), was a proper act to regulate the situation of migrants and potential asylum seekers (more on that in the further part of the article). In other words, there was another – next to the violation of international obligations – possible legal ground for deeming the regulation unconstitutional.

At the end of 2021, the Polish public opinion generally thought that the actions undertaken by the Polish government³⁷ were good³⁸. Such views were shared by the supporters of the then-government and people of a more right-wing worldview, whereas the then-opposition's electorate was strongly against the policies concerning the crisis on the border. Surprisingly from the human rights perspective, when it came to the issue of whether to allow the migrants on the Polish–Belarusian border to file motions for international protection, majority thought it should not be allowed (from 52% respondents in September, 2021, to 58% in December, 2021). These findings, however, could be explained by the fact that back then the topic of the crisis at the border was constantly

³⁵ Art. 303b section 1 of the Act of 12.12.2003 on Foreigners (Journal of Laws of Republic of Poland of 2023, item 519, as amended).

³⁶ Art. 299 of the Act of 12.12.2003 on Foreigners (Journal of Laws of Republic of Poland of 2023, item 519, as amended).

³⁷ These action included not only the described in this article changes in migration law, but also the plans – and later, their execution – to build a wall on the Polish–Belarusian border. This idea was supported by 66% of the respondents of the CBOS research, cited below. What is beyond interesting, is that among these supporters were people voting at every political option in Poland.

³⁸ Centrum Badań Opinii Społecznej, *Komunikat z badań. Opinia publiczna wobec kryzysu na granicy z Białorusią*, <https://www.cbos.pl/SPISKOM.POL/2021/K_160_21.PDF>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

being repeated in the media, and usually shown in a very negative light. The amount of news from the border eventually led to the public getting accustomed to this situation, so it can be said that the crisis, although still happening, got somehow „normalized” in the eyes of the Polish society³⁹.

2.3. Migrant Protection Protocols in Polish reality

Having shortly described how U.S. and Poland tried to deal with crises at their borders, one can wonder what relation could be between MPP and changes in Polish migration law, particularly the regulation of March 13, 2020. The question here is, whether MPP could be applied in Poland, or perhaps – whether their objectives already were, but under different name. It seems that both sets of regulations allowed for removing some groups of migrants (those deemed „inadmissible”, meaning mostly those who crossed the border illegally, with no documentation), in order to, among other reasons, relieve the overwhelmed and overcrowded system of migrant detention centers. Both these initiatives have created a specific atmosphere in the near-border-area⁴⁰, causing concern among human rights activists and local communities. Although the circumstances of introducing the changes in Poland were not the same as in the U.S. (push-backs in Poland were deployed before the COVID-19 pandemic hit, but the changes in law were introduced in 2020 with the first objective to address the pandemic-related threats), the thesis that parts of MPP could be found in Polish regulations seems not to be a far-fetched one. The main differences would regard mostly the kind of authorities competent to return migrants to the territory, from which they crossed the border, and the asylum proceedings, which in Poland were not always a given. The overall objectives, however, seem to be the same.

3. *Biden v. Texas*

3.1. Fact pattern and procedural history

The Migrant Protection Protocols were suspended on January 20, 2021 by Secretary Alejandro Mayorkas. What followed was the issuing of the presidential Executive Order No. 14010, which aimed at reviewing this policy and determining, whether the MPP should be terminated or modified. As a result, MPP were officially terminated on June 1, 2021, having been deemed not adequate or sustainable so as to justify such strong means as returning some migrants to Mexico, in order to improve border security. This action (the June 1 Memorandum) was not met without criticism. Some accusations involved the matter of whether such a termination could have been

³⁹ M. Chrzczonowicz, *Kryminalizacja pomocy, militaryzacja granic. Co robi władza na granicy polsko-białoruskiej?*, <<https://oko.press/kryminalizacja-pomocy-militaryzacja-granic>>, [accessed: 18.3.2024].

⁴⁰ Like state of emergency in the area near Polish–Belarusian border.

made in light of the Immigration and Nationality Act (INA), or (to be more exact) 8 U.S.C. section 1225(b)(2), which says that when the detention of an „inadmissible” alien is not possible, „the Attorney General may return the alien to that territory pending a proceeding under section 1229a of this title [8 U.S.C.]”⁴¹. The States of Texas and Missouri, who later initiated the lawsuit against President Biden (which is the object of analysis here), claimed that this section made it obligatory to return an „inadmissible” alien to Mexico, when the detention is not possible. Therefore, they claimed, the termination of MPP violates the law.

The District Court in Northern District of Texas, Amarillo Division held that the Biden administration’s conduct violated the Immigration and Nationality Act (INA)⁴², because the return policy was mandatory as long as the detention of said migrants was not possible. The release of these people into the U.S. territory was, in the view of the District Court, a systematic violation of § 1225. It also held that the Administrative Procedure Act (APA)⁴³ was violated by the attempted rescission from MPP due to lack of reasoned decision-making, which resulted in the Secretary’s action being arbitrary and capricious⁴⁴. Additionally, it imposed a nationwide injunction, ordering the government to „enforce and implement MPP in good faith until such a time as it has been lawfully rescinded in compliance with the APA and such a time as the federal government has sufficient detention capacity to detain all aliens subject to mandatory detention under [section 1225] without releasing any aliens because of lack of detention resources”⁴⁵. What has to be noticed is that through this judgment, the District Court broke „long-standing precedent cautioning judicial restraint and deference to the political branches in matters relating to foreign affairs”⁴⁶. Previously, the American courts have steered from this topic. On October 29, 2021 Secretary Mayorkas issued new memoranda that announced the termination of MPP, saying that the program’s benefits did not justify the costs, especially given the way it influenced the U.S.–Mexican relations.

The Court of Appeals in the Fifth Circuit affirmed the District Court’s judgment, agreeing on the interpretation of the section 1225(b)(2). Moreover, the Court held that the October 29 Memoranda did not constitute a new and separately reviewable „final agency action”, but simply explained the DHS’ reasoning from the June 1

⁴¹ Immigration and Nationality Act, 8 U.S.C. § 1225(b)(2)(C).

⁴² Immigration and Nationality Act, 8 U.S.C. § 1101 et seq.

⁴³ Administrative Procedure Act, 5 U.S.C. § 701 et seq.

⁴⁴ Decision of the United States District Court, Northern District of Texas of 13.8.2021, *Texas v. Biden*, 554 F.Supp.3d 818 (2021), p. 847–851.

⁴⁵ Decision of the United States District Court, Northern District of Texas of 13.8.2021, *Texas v. Biden*, 554 F.Supp.3d 818 (2021), p. 857.

⁴⁶ H. Damon-Feng, *Asylum, Interrupted*, „Harvard Law & Policy Review Blog” 2022, p. 4, <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3923247>, [accessed: 19.3.2024].

Memorandum⁴⁷, as a way to defend the Termination Decision in the Court of Appeals⁴⁸.

3.2. The Supreme Court's holding

The important thing, which, despite being deductible from the procedural history shortly described above, still has to be acknowledged at the very beginning, is that the Supreme Court did not concern itself with the question, whether MPP were legal, i.e. whether the politics of returning migrants to Mexico to await the resolution of the proceedings in the U.S. were compatible with the law (both domestic and international). The issues, the Court faced, were quite different, and involved more technical matters, namely the way and art of terminating MPP by the Secretary. The question of legality or illegality of MPP was not posed here, and so, in this segment of the article, this issue is not further analyzed. Were this case heard before a Polish administrative court, it would probably have been a little bit different, as they take into account the possibility of the proceedings being void, no matter if the petitioner brings it up.

The most important issue in the *Biden v. Texas* is, whether the Migrant Protection Protocols (MPP), introduced by the DHS under the Trump Administration in January 2019, were correctly suspended (and eventually, terminated) by the actions taken by Biden Administration. However, that was not the only question the Supreme Court had to answer.

The first thing the Supreme Court acknowledged was the issue of jurisdiction – whether the District Court was competent to impose the injunction. In answering this question, the Supreme Court interpreted section 1252(f)(1), saying that it did not strip lower courts of the subject matter jurisdiction *per se*, but only withdrew their power to grant a specific form of injunctive relief⁴⁹, unless it regarded a specific individual alien. Indisputable was that the Supreme Court had jurisdiction in this case and was competent to impose an injunction (independently from the previously and wrongfully imposed one)⁵⁰. Only after having cleared that out, had the Supreme Court acknowledged the main issues of *Biden v. Texas* – the allegations of violations of INA and APA.

The section in question, § 1225(b)(2)(C), in its disposition uses the word „may”. When interpreted together with the § 1225(b)(2)(A) (obligatory character of which

⁴⁷ Decision of the United States Court of Appeals, Fourth Circuit of 13.12.2021, *Texas v. Biden*, 20 F.4th 928 (2021), p. 951.

⁴⁸ Decision of the United States Court of Appeals, Fourth Circuit of 13.12.2021, *Texas v. Biden*, 20 F.4th 928 (2021), p. 941.

⁴⁹ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 798.

⁵⁰ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 801.

was not disputed in this opinion), in the District Court and the Court of Appeals' opinions this section obliges the authorities to return „inadmissible” aliens, who cannot be placed in detention due to the organizational matters (e.g. overpopulation in detention centers). Before summarizing, what the Supreme Court held, one thing has to be made clear: when it comes to interpreting a statute or any other legal act, courts usually do so according to one of two most popular theories in the U.S., textualism or purposivism⁵¹. In this case, it was pretty clear that the Court followed the literal meaning of the word „may”, and supported its arguments by fleeing into the systematic interpretation of INA.

The Court's concluded that „section 1225(b)(2)(C) means what it says: ‘may’ means ‘may’, and INA itself does not require the Secretary to continue exercising his discretionary authority under these circumstances”⁵². The sentence in itself seems like a pleonasm, and does not explain much, and it could be argued that this whole passage of Court's opinion seems a little bit redundant. The Supreme Court said at the very beginning, that it „repeatedly observed that the word ‘may’ clearly connotes discretion”⁵³, citing numerous cases⁵⁴. That does not cause many doubts, as the literal definition of the word „may” is „used to indicate possibility or probability; sometimes used interchangeably with can; sometimes used where might would be expected”⁵⁵.

Moreover, the history of Immigration and Nationality Act seems to support the Court's interpretation, as the section 1225(b)(2)(C) was added about 90 years after section 1225(b)(2)(A) with the aim of justifying the longstanding practice of Immigration and Naturalization Service (INS) to return some aliens to Mexico or Canada, which had been questioned by the Board of Immigration Appeals. This historical context helps to understand that the section in question was not meant to be a mandatory „safety valve” for aliens who were not detained. Quite the contrary – it only confirmed the authority of Secretary to engage in practice of returning „inadmissible” aliens, when their detention is not possible. Furthermore, before MPP was introduced, section

⁵¹ *Statutory construction*, <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/statutory_construction>, [accessed: 19.3.2024].

⁵² Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 807.

⁵³ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 802.

⁵⁴ E.g. Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 24.2.2020, *Opati v. Republic of Sudan*, 590 U. S. ----, ----, 140 S.Ct. 1601, 1609, 206 L.Ed.2d 904 (2020); Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 27.11.2018, *Weyerhaeuser Co. v. United States Fish and Wildlife Serv.*, 586 U. S. ----, ----, 139 S.Ct. 361, 371, 202 L.Ed.2d 269 (2018); Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 12.1.2005, *Jama v. Immigration and Customs Enforcement*, 543 U.S. 335, 346, 125 S.Ct. 694, 160 L.Ed.2d 708(2005).

⁵⁵ *May* [in:] *Mirriam Webster Dictionary*, <<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/may>>, [accessed: 19.3.2024].

1225(b)(2)(C) was used by every administration as purely discretionary; only during MPP was it interpreted as an obligation⁵⁶.

One more thing taken into consideration by the Supreme Court: international affairs issue. Had „may” meant an obligation, it would have eventually had a huge (and not necessarily positive) impact on the U.S.–Mexican relations. MPP was made possible thanks to a bilateral agreement between these two countries, although it has to be noticed that the United States had a much stronger position, and a lot of pressure was put on the Mexican government⁵⁷. Any negotiations would not be possible, if section 1225(b)(2)(C) meant every „inadmissible” alien, who cannot be put in a detention center, has to be returned to Mexico, as the executive’s hands would have been tied in that kind of situation⁵⁸.

The most important argument, however, revolved around the competences of Supreme Court and Congress. The view adopted by the Court would have been, what in Poland would be called „reasonable legislator’s assumption”. As it said in *Jama v. Immigration and Customs Enforcement*, the Court „do[es] not lightly assume that Congress has omitted from its adopted text requirements that it nonetheless intends to apply”⁵⁹. In other words, it is not the Court’s role to assume that the legislator erred in adopting some kind of rule, as a result of which the Court has to fill in the gaps by adding some words or changing their meaning entirely. It is assumed that the legislator acts with a forethought, consciously, and therefore the judicature must not „overread” what the text already says. Whether this assumption is true or false, is not questioned by the Court.

All this reasoning led to the Court holding that section 1225(b)(2)(C) is of a discretionary nature and due to that the termination of MPP did not violate INA.

When the Court turned to the question of alleged violation of APA, it distinguished between two different actions an agency can undertake, when its action had been deemed inadequate by a court. Based on *Department of Homeland Security v. Regents of University of California*, the agency can either offer a fuller explanation of the agency’s reasoning at the time of the agency action, or it can take a completely new agency action, in which it will be not limited to its prior reasons⁶⁰. The Court of Appeals in the Ninth Circuit held that the October 29 Memoranda were the first type, however the Supreme Court reversed and held that it did, in fact, constitute a final, valid action. According to the Court, the words used in the October 29 Memoranda („I hereby supersede

⁵⁶ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 804–807.

⁵⁷ I. Gil-Everaert, C. Masferrer, S.R. Chávez, *Concurrent...*, p. 131.

⁵⁸ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 806.

⁵⁹ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 12.1.2005, *Jama v. Immigration and Customs Enforcement*, 543 U.S. 335 (2005), p. 341.

⁶⁰ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 18.6.2020, *Department of Homeland Security v. Regents of University of California*, 140 S.Ct. 1891 (2020), p. 1908.

and rescind the June 1 memorandum”) indicated that this action should be viewed as a way to deal with the problem afresh⁶¹.

Therefore, the Court held that Secretary Mayorkas’ actions did not violate APA, either, and reversed the Court of Appeals’ judgment altogether⁶².

3.3. *Biden v. Texas* in Polish reality

What would be interesting now, is taking a look at *Biden v. Texas* from Polish perspective. Assuming MPP would have been in force in Poland, and the same kinds of issues would have been raised, would Polish court have reached the same conclusions?

Starting from the jurisdiction question. Were this case about the legality (compliance with Constitution) of such program, it would seem that the Polish Constitutional Tribunal would have been competent to adjudicate. Here, the issue would have been about the legality of state authority’s action to terminate that program (in Poland that would probably be either a minister through regulations, or legislature through statute – depending, how „Polish MPP” came into being) in light of migration law and administrative procedure, therefore it is safe to assume that the Tribunal would hear this case, too. That way, its holding would have a universal effect in the Polish legal system. A different court could analyze such issue, but only with regard to a single, particular case. Of course, since these remarks are purely hypothetical, it is assumed that in this scenario there are no controversies about Tribunal’s standing, work and its judges, and therefore the case would have been heard there.

When it comes to the issue of interpreting the word „may”, it would have seem that Polish Tribunal would come to the same, or only slightly different conclusions as the Supreme Court of the U.S. The „reasonable legislator assumption”, although causing many doubts, would be applied here, and together with rules of literal, historical, systematic and functional legal interpretation (probably a bit wider than the American textual one) would have provided with the same results.

On the other hand, it is probable that the second issue (about the alleged APA violation) would have not been raised before the Tribunal, as there is only one instance and no appeal from its judgment. Therefore, there would have not been a situation, in which the authority has to „repeat” its action to terminate „Polish MPP”. Perhaps a question of statutory authorization could have come up, but this goes beyond these

⁶¹ Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States of 30.6.2022, *Biden v. Texas*, 597 U.S. 785 (2022), p. 811.

⁶² What is worth mentioning at the end, and which was not a part of the majority opinion, was Justice Alito’s dissent. He observed a unique practice in the Supreme Court’s judicature and claimed that as a general rule, difficult jurisdictional questions (such as the matter resolved in *Biden v. Texas*) are resolved in favor of the government, despite lack of sufficient proofs in favor of the government. When one looks closer at this case, it is probably safe to assume it is true (Justice Alito wrote of „only hurried briefing and no argument”), although in this particular circumstances the government’s stance on there being no violation of INA and APA was seemingly right.

hypothetical musings. At the moment, it could be said that had *Biden v. Texas* been heard before the Polish Constitutional Tribunal, the holding would have been pretty much the same.

4. Jurisprudence on the migration policies on the Polish–Belarusian border

The problem about Polish new regulations concerning the situation on the Polish–Belarusian border is that, although the changes made in the migration law are similar to MPP in what their effects were, the response from the judiciary is quite different. The reasons are dissimilarly built court systems and different place of the initiatives in question in the legal acts hierarchies, not to mention slightly different questions posed before the courts.

First, Poland is a unitary, not federal (like the U.S.) state, therefore there is no problem with deciding which courts (federal or state) have the subject matter jurisdiction. However, it is not courts of general jurisdiction, but administrative courts, which adjudicated *inter alia* in cases of international protection, aliens' legal and illegal stay in Poland and their deportation. Secondly, the changes, that are the subject of analysis in this article, were made on two levels. There is the regulation of the Minister of Internal Affairs and Administration and the Act on Foreigners. What is important, is that only the Polish Constitutional Tribunal is competent to declare a legal act unconstitutional, which – although not that different from the Supreme Court of the United States' competence – poses a significant problem in current situation, when the Tribunal's standing causes a lot of controversies. However, based on the diffuse constitutionality review doctrine⁶³, the unconstitutionality of singular statutes and regulations can be acknowledged by the lower courts, in that they decide not to use them as a legal basis in a single case. This has to suffice until such statute or regulation is amended or terminated by proper authority, and removed from the legal system altogether.

The following part of the article will present some of the opinions of Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok, so as to show that the judiciary has dealt with the issue of changes to migration law in numerous cases so far. As was mentioned above, the few chosen cases are meant to show the reader some broader context and sense of understanding of the Polish jurisprudence in the matter – however, since *Biden v. Texas* is of bigger importance for this article (as its inspiration and a kind of starting point), they will not be as closely examined as the Supreme Court's opinion.

⁶³ More on the diffuse constitutionality review doctrine e.g. J. Podkowik, *O przyczynach, przejawach i skutkach rozproszonej kontroli konstytucyjności ustaw (w świetle orzecznictwa sądów powszechnych i Sądu Najwyższego)*, „Studia Prawnicze” 2022, No 2 (226), p. 107–132.

4.1. Jurisprudence on the Regulation of the Minister of the Interior Affairs and Administration of March 13, 2020 on the temporary suspension or declaration of cross-border traffic on the most fortunate border points

The exact thing that was closely analyzed by Polish administrative courts in the following cases was the administrative action of chiefs of border guard who turned back migrants, who illegally crossed the Polish–Belarusian border, to the border line. The judiciary agrees that such an action can be a cause for action before administrative courts⁶⁴.

There were a few issues that administrative courts considered. One of them was the legality of issuing the amendments from August 2021 (*supra*), which concerned the migrants who crossed the border illegally. The legal basis for the Minister of Internal Affairs and Administration's regulation of March 13, 2020 and the following changes was article 16 section 3 point 2 of the Act of October 12, 1990 on Protection of State Border⁶⁵, which gives the Minister of Internal Affairs and Administration discretion to issue a regulation temporarily regulating or limiting the traffic on border points in certain circumstances. It says nothing of migrants' or international protection's matters. Moreover, it applies only to the territory of Poland – but foreigners, who were found outside border points, were also pushed-back after the amendments in August 2021⁶⁶. This kind of argumentation was brought up by the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok⁶⁷, which held that the regulation of March 13, 2020 (and its amendments) was issued in violation of article 92 section 1 sentence 1 of the Polish Constitution. In other words, it encompassed more situations than the statutory authorization (legal basis for this legal act) meant to, as the article 16 of the Act on Protection of State Border does not say anything about foreigners or competences of chiefs of border guard officers outside border points⁶⁸.

⁶⁴ E.g. Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 492/22, LEX no 3411630; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 493/22, LEX no 3411543; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 494/22, LEX no 3411599; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 30.5.2023, II SA/Bk 244/23, LEX no 3573112; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 13.4.2023, II SA/Bk 145/23, LEX no 3546573; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 18.1.2024, II SA/Bk 664/23, LEX no 3665838. .

⁶⁵ Act of 12.10.1990 on protection of state borders (Journal of Laws of Republic of Poland of 2024, item 388).

⁶⁶ J. Chlebny, *Zawrócenie cudzoziemca na granicy*, „Zeszyty Naukowe Sądownictwa Administracyjnego” 2023, Vol. 5 (110), p. 20.

⁶⁷ Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 492/22, LEX no 3411630.

⁶⁸ Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 5.3.2024, II SA/Bk 71/24, LEX no 3693006.

Given that, it was clear that the action of returning migrants to the border line based on § 3 section 2b was ineffective, as was the paragraph itself, which was later confirmed in many more judgments on this topic⁶⁹.

4.2. Jurisprudence on the art. 303b of the Act of December 12, 2003 on Foreigners

On the other hand, the newly introduced article 303b of the Act on Foreigners is generally not deemed completely unconstitutional or in violation of international/European law, due to some discretionary power given to states in matters of „illegal” migration⁷⁰. However, this rule requires some concretizing through interpretation, as the administrative courts have said.

As was mentioned above, art. 303b of the Act on Foreigners introduced to Polish migration law a new ground for obliging a foreigner to leave the territory of Poland, if said foreigner was detained immediately after illegally crossing the external border of the EU. Such a decision can be appealed, but its execution is not stopped, which means that after deportation the appeal is *de facto* rendered pointless – the same can be said about an international protection application, for which the foreigner can theoretically apply, but after deportation is being left unprocessed⁷¹. Since one of the problems with the art. 303b was that it seemed to legalize some kinds of pushbacks, the main issue that the courts have to tackle in cases regarding aforementioned regulation is whether the non-refoulement rule was in turn breached.

The Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok stated that „to implement the non-refoulement rule, first and foremost, the interested parties have to be informed of their rights and be asked of the possible dangers concerning them [possible dangers that could await them, had they been deported from Poland – P.P.]”⁷². In this case, the Court found that this duty of border guard officers was not fulfilled, and the petitioner’s claim was well-based. What is also important: when a person, who was turned back to the border line, faces dangers listed in the article 3 of the European Convention of Human Rights (prohibition of torture), the appeal has to have a suspending effect

⁶⁹ Such conclusions were made in several opinions, e.g. Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 492/22, LEX no 3411630; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 493/22, LEX no 3411543; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 15.9.2022, II SA/Bk 494/22, LEX no 3411599; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 13.4.2023, II SA/Bk 145/23, LEX no 3546573; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 30.5.2023, II SA/Bk 244/23, LEX no 3573112; Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 5.3.2024, II SA/Bk 71/24, LEX no 3693006.

⁷⁰ J. Chlebny, *Zawrócenie...*, p. 21–22.

⁷¹ G. Baranowska, *Legalność i dopuszczalność procedury push-back (wywózek) i ocena prób ich legalizowania w Polsce* [in:] *Poza prawem: Prawna ocena działań Państwa Polskiego w reakcji na kryzys humanitarny na granicy polsko-białoruskiej*, ed. W. Klaus, Warszawa 2022, p. 12.

⁷² Judgment of the Provincial Administrative Court in Białystok of 27.10.2022, II SA/Bk 558/22, LEX no 3434298.

on the deportation of said person⁷³. This makes a lot of sense, when one looks at the MPP example (*supra*), and the much weaker position of migrants, who were returned to Mexico, and had smaller chances in succeeding in the legal proceedings concerning their asylum status.

5. Conclusion

What could be surprising for a reader not acquainted with the issues presented in this article, is that the regulations analyzed here (MPP and regulation of March 13 as amended, and amendments to the Act on Foreigners mentioned above) are still in force in some ways – despite there being quite an impressive jurisprudence on why they are either illegal, or require closer and detailed interpretation. Although MPP was formally terminated in October 2022, its ramifications have not „magically” disappeared (also because it was intertwined with many other initiatives, as mentioned previously).

The cases cited in this article, with the main focus at *Biden v. Texas*, dealt with slightly different questions, although all of them were about the migration law as amended in light of the crises at the U.S.–Mexican and Polish–Belarusian borders. The first one focused on the legality of Secretary’s action to terminate MPP, while the latest jurisprudence of Polish administrative courts (with most of the opinions issued by the court in Białystok) revolved around the legality of the acts (regulation of March 13, 2020 and the amended Act on Foreigners) themselves. This difference plays a huge role, also from the court system point of view. The Supreme Court’s opinion applies for all the U.S., while each opinion of the administrative court applies only for a particular case. Of course, it can be cited as a sort of primary authority in another case, but it does not have the same universal effect as, for example, the Constitutional Tribunal’s would have. What has to be remembered is that technically there is no common law system in Poland, which would make judicial opinions law, though in reality citations are very much powerful; however, only on the judicial-decisions-level, not when it comes to influencing the reality of migration control. Previous opinions or opinions of different courts are taken under consideration⁷⁴.

Essentially, it is probable that Polish courts would have reached the same conclusions as the Supreme Court have in *Biden v. Texas* in a factually similar case, either based on the U.S. law, or Polish. When it comes to interpretation rules, it seems that they are pretty similar, and literal, historical, systematic and functional interpretations would have the same results. It seems also that both American and Polish courts follow the „reasonable legislator assumption” doctrine.

⁷³ M. Górczyńska, *Zakres gwarancji proceduralnych przysługujących cudzoziemcom zawracanym na Białoruś po przekroczeniu granicy wbrew przepisom prawa – glosa do wyroku Wojewódzkiego Sądu Administracyjnego w Białymstoku z 27.10.2022 r., II SA/Bk 558/22*, „Europejski Przegląd Sądowy” 2023, No 8, p. 60.

⁷⁴ More on the role of precedent in Polish law: A. Gross, *Rola precedensu w porządku prawa stanowionego w Polsce – wprowadzenie do problematyki*, „Acta Iuris Stetinensis” 2022, Vol. 38, No 2, p. 109–121.

The conclusion is as follows. It seems that in dealing with the crises at their borders, both the U.S. and Poland valued very much (or perhaps even overvalued) the importance of state sovereignty, even at the cost of human rights and international obligations, and sometimes perhaps some humanitarianism. This similarity is quite surprising, because both countries have different law systems (common v. continental law), different experiences with multiculturalism and migration (United States being a multinational country with a long history of migration; Poland as a whole country being mostly homogenous when it comes to nationality⁷⁵, though near the Polish–Belarusian border the situation differs a bit), and different geopolitical positions (with the USA having the possibility of cooperating with Mexico, and Poland having no such option when it comes to the Belarusian regime) – yet in times of crises the adopted solutions are very alike, at least when it comes to their objectives and the eventual outcome.

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⁷⁵ According to the data from the National Population and Housing Census of 2021, 98,84% of people living in Poland declare they are of Polish nationality. *National Population and Housing Census 2021 Population. Size and demographic-social structure in the light of the 2021 Census results*, Warsaw 2023, p. 114, Table 7.1., <https://stat.gov.pl/download/gfx/portalinformacyjny/en/defaultaktualnosci/3701/6/1/1/national_population_and_housing_census_2021_population_2.pdf>, [accessed: 8.10.2024].

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